

COMPOSITION OF PRUSSIAN AND TURNBULL'S BLUES. PART VII. VISCOSITY IN RELATION TO COMPOSITION

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The viscosity of the colloidal Prussian and Turnbull's blues has been determined at various stages of dialysis and dilution and at several temperatures. It has been observed by plotting the values of viscosity against (i) the days of dialysis, and (ii) against dilution, that at the same temperatures the viscosity curves are remarkably similar in shape showing that the composition of the colloidal Prussian and Turnbull's blues also tend to become identical. Changes in viscosity with temperature lead to the same conclusion.

The view that the electric charge on the suspensoid particles contribute to the viscosity of the system containing such particles was first put forward by Smoluchowski (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1913, 9, 35). This view was further supported by Ostwald and Hatschek in their study on the viscosities of various hydrosols.

Dhar and Gore (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 641) carried out investigations on the changes of viscosity of many colloids and observed that the lesser the charge on the colloids, the greater was its hydration and hence greater was the viscosity. They observed a definite relation between viscosity and purity of various hydroxide sols, but could not establish any definite relation in the case of arsenic and antimony sulphide sols as well as copper ferrocyanide and Prussian blue sols. The reason for the irregular behaviour was supposed to be due to their gradual hydrolysis with the progress of dialysis.

In this paper, we have discussed the results of our investigations on the behaviour of Prussian and Turnbull's blue sols from the view point of their viscosity at various stages of dialysis and temperature. From the viscosity of these sols we have attempted to throw some light on the similarity of their composition as well.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Sols.—In order to bring Prussian blue in the colloidal state excess of potassium ferrocyanide was used and it was found that, on mixing one equivalent of ferric chloride with 5/4 equivalents of potassium ferrocyanide, a fairly stable sol was obtained. A more stable sol was prepared by mixing the reactants in the ratio of one equivalent to 1.5 equivalents.

Turnbull's blue was brought into the colloidal state by using excess of potassium ferricyanide solution. It was found that on mixing one equivalent of ferrous sulphate with 1.5 equivalents of potassium ferricyanide a fairly stable sol was obtained.

Measurement of Viscosity.—Scarpa's method (*Gazzetta*, 1910, 40, 271) modified by Farrow (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 347) and improved by Prasad, Mehta and Desai (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 1384) was followed. An ordinary viscometer was kept in an electrically heated thermostat and a suction at a pressure of 15 cm. of water was applied throughout our investigations in order to cause the upward flow of liquid into the viscometer. The apparatus constant K was determined at several temperatures by the formula :

$$\eta_{t^0} = K \frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2},$$

where η_{t^0} = the absolute viscosity of water at t^0 ,

t_1 = time required by the liquid to rise from the lower to the upper mark,

t_2 = time required by the liquid to fall from the upper to the lower mark.

The values of K at different temperatures are given below :

Temp. ...	21°	25°	27.5°	30°	32.5°	35°
K ...	0.001336	0.001211	0.001202	0.001171	0.001140	0.001117

The apparatus was standardised before it was used for measurement of the viscosity of the sols. The concentration of the sol on each day of dialysis was kept constant and the viscosity of the original sol 'A' and those of twice and four times diluted ones ("A/2" and "A/4") were also observed.

Results have been presented in graphs. Fig. 1 gives the variations in viscosity with the progress of dialysis for Prussian blue and Turnbull's blue prepared with iron salt : potassium salt in the ratio (1 : 1.5). Fig. 2 shows the same results for Prussian blue prepared in the ratio of iron to potassium salts as 1 : 1.25.

Variations of viscosity with dilution at different stages of dialysis for both Prussian blue and Turnbull's blue sols prepared with iron salt : potassium salt in the ratio of 1 : 3/2 have been graphically shown in Fig. 3.

DISCUSSION

From the foregoing results it will be observed that the viscosity of both these sols gradually rises as the purity increases for the first four days, after which there is a fall. Fig. 1 shows this effect very clearly.

Dhar and collaborators observed that no definite relation regarding the viscosity and the purity of the sol could be established in the case of hydrolysable sols, such as Prussian blue, arsenic and antimony sulphide sols. Our investigations, however, show that Prussian and Turnbull's blue sols behave upto a certain stage of dialysis in the same way as unhydrolysable sols which exhibit increase in viscosity as their purity increases by dialysis. The viscosity values in the curves clearly show that there is a regular increase in the viscosity of the Prussian and Turnbull's blue sols for the first four days of dialysis, and then on further dialysis, the viscosity begins to decrease. A scrutiny of the curves will show, that the maximum increase in viscosity takes place on the first day of dialysis and then the rate of increase becomes less and less till the fourth day, when the viscosity reaches maximum. On the fifth and sixth days there is a decrease. This can be explained by assuming that there are two different states of the colloid during the course of its dialysis. The first state of the sol corresponds with the view advocated by Dhar and Gore (*loc. cit.*) that the viscosity increases with the hydration of colloidal particle caused by the dialysis of the sol, and the second state is one where the progressive hydration stops and then the hydrolysis of the sol follows.

It is further observed that the viscosity maximum (Fig. 2) reaches on the second day

FIG. 2

Changes in viscosity with dialysis of P.B. sol (1 : 5/4).

of dialysis in the case of the sol's prepared by mixing the reactants in the ratio of one equivalent to 5/4 equivalents, whereas the viscosity maximum of the sol prepared by mixing one equivalent of ferric chloride with 3/2 equivalents of potassium ferrocyanide reaches on the fourth day. Turnbull's blue sol prepared by mixing the reactants in the ratio of one equivalent to 5/4 equivalents was not very stable while that prepared by mixing the reactants in the ratio of one equivalent to 3/2 equivalents shows a similar maximum on the fourth day of dialysis. This observation suggests that the similarity of behaviour of these two sols is much influenced by the amount of potassium ferro- and ferricyanide added in excess during their preparation.

FIG. 3

Their behaviour on dilution at different stages of dialysis (Fig. 3) shows that the changes in viscosity with dilution are such as to yield curves of similar shape.

The relation between the changes in viscosity with temperature shown by Prussian and Turnbull's blue sols seems to be almost linear and the straight lines thus obtained for the respective sols begin to overlap each other after the third day of dialysis.

Bhattacharya and Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 213, 248) advanced the view that precipitated Prussian and Turnbull's blues should have similar composition. This view was supported by analytical results as well as by physical properties such as absorption

FIG. 4

Relation between temperature and viscosity for P.B. sol (x : 3/2).

FIG. 5

Relation between temperature and viscosity for T.B. sol (x : 3/2).

spectra and magnetic susceptibility of such compounds as were prepared by the ageing method (Bhattacharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 325; 1935, 12, 143; 1941, 18, 71). By studying the viscosities of the sols of Prussian and Turnbull's blues, we conclude that the composition of the colloidal solutions prepared by mixing one equivalent to $3/2$ equivalents also tend to approach each other very closely as has been observed in the case of the precipitates of aged Prussian and Turnbull's blues by Bhattacharya. The little shift between the closely approaching curves having identical shapes as in Fig. 1, only suggests that there is some difference in the size of the colloidal particles of Prussian and Turnbull's blues while the chemical composition of these two colloidal substances as judged from these curves seems to be the same. The mutual oxidation and reduction between the reactants is much greater when potassium ferrocyanide or ferricyanide is added in excess to ferric chloride and ferrous sulphate respectively than when the reactants are mixed in equivalent proportion. It is due to this effect followed by the adsorption of ferro- or ferricyanogen ions that the composition of the sols of Prussian and Turnbull's blues shows such a marked similarity as can be judged from the changes of their viscosities with dialysis.

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